

Confronting Challenges Of Implementing Accounting Curriculum In A Context Of Curriculum Change In Selected South African Township Secondary Schools

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 01 , 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 08, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Curriculum change, Curriculum implementation, Curriculum management Teaching approaches</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7707139</p>	<p><i>This study engaged on the persistent challenges encountered by Accounting teachers on curriculum implementation due to the ever-evolving curriculum since the introduction of a democratic state in South Africa. This study was underpinned by Piaget's theory of cognitive development, transformation theory and Maslow's theory of motivation. The study utilised a qualitative case study design. Through purposive sampling, seventeen Accounting teachers and five principals were selected from seventeen township secondary schools which represented (10%) of secondary schools offering Accounting. Semi-structured interviews and document analysis were used to generate data. Data was analysed using thematic content analysis which is mostly used in qualitative research studies. The findings revealed that many Accounting teachers have not adapted to the pedagogical content of the new curriculum due to the numerous fundamental challenges. The study recommended amongst others, that the Department of Basic Education (DBE) to consider reviewing Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) regarding Economic and Management Sciences (EMS) in General Education and Training (GET) phase and make Accounting a stand-alone subject; and the DBE to work in collaboration with the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) to review Accounting and Mathematics as subject combinations into Accounting.</i></p>

Introduction

Post South African democratic elections in 1994, the new Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (Act 108 of 1996) was adopted to provide the foundation for curriculum transformation and development in South Africa (Mathebe, 2021). This curriculum transformation was set to democratise the education system that was historically based on racial inequalities. Curriculum reform brought about many changes to the culture of learning and teaching. "Owing to this, the change from Curriculum 2005, usually referred to as Outcomes-Based Education (OBE) led to the introduction of the Revised National Curriculum Statement (RNCS), then the National Curriculum Statement (NCS) and now the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS)" (Kretzer & Oluoch-Suleh, 2022, p. 2). This has brought significant changes compared to the old curriculum (NATED 550).

Subsequently, Padayachee and Van Niekerk (2019) posit that the Accounting curriculum has drastically changed its form with the new curriculum introduced since the government of the African National Congress (ANC) took over in 1994. This threatens teachers who were trained long before these changes were effected. The ANC-led government upon ascending to power in 1994 the White Paper on Education and Training (1995) that provides a framework on how new curricula can be developed was adopted and published. Significant directives that are emphasised in this paper amongst others involve an inclusive strategy for education and training, an output-orientated approach, ultimate learning, access to basic education and training to all, redress, equity and transformation of the legacies of the past (Mda & Mothata, 2000). This study recognises the NCS as the main curriculum for South African basic education and that CAPS deals with practical guidelines and directives to the implementation of NCS. NCS replaced the historic curriculum under the apartheid government in the quest to correct the imbalances of the past. "It intended to promote the values of human rights, inclusivity, environmental and social justice to all South Africans, as well as to develop an internationally competitive nation with literate, creative and critically thinking citizens" (DoE, 2003' p. 12).

Since the Accounting curriculum has drastically changed its form with the introduction of NCS, the change has required the Accounting subject to be redesigned and reconceptualised. The old curriculum (NATED 550) mainly focused on financial record-keeping, which forced learners to depend only on memorising (Letshwene, 2014). The researchers are of the view that learners were not taught to reason and reflect on financial

information for the purpose of solving problems and making informed decisions. The NCS implementation resulted in the content of the Accounting discipline gravitating towards a redefined curriculum. Additional to the financial record-keeping, it added managerial accounting and managing resources. This brought, amongst other critical topics, cost management, management controls, audit cycles and Business ethics.

Another critical change was when the EMS was introduced to the general education and training (GET) band (Grades 7-9). EMS constitutes (40%) of financial literacy (Accounting), (30%) of entrepreneurship (Business Studies) and (30%) of the economy (Economics). It serves as a basis for all these three subjects in the further education and training (FET) band (Grades 10-12). The question that arises is whether it is possible for one teacher to be qualified to teach all three subjects. However, Phakathi (2019) and Ntshangase (2017) claim that EMS teachers in the GET phase are generally not competent to teach Accounting, although (40%) of the Accounting content is allocated to the subject. Furthermore, Ntshangase (2017) posits that the notional time allocated to EMS in grades 8 and 9 is only two hours per week, making it difficult for teachers to cover the expected curriculum and this is indeed a drawback in setting a strong foundation for FET. This will mean learners join the FET band without adequate basic knowledge for them to grasp the required aspects of Accounting as a subject. Arguably, this study responded to whether this is a reality and can be generalised as the problem.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The Accounting curriculum transition from NATED 550 to NCS/CAPS has involved the introduction of new content material, and a portion of old content material being removed, whilst the approaches to teachings and assessments in Accounting have also drastically changed. This curriculum change has negatively affected teachers as the majority of them got their qualification before the new topics were added or were never trained using innovative approaches of the new Accounting pedagogy and therefore challenges have been reported regarding the new curriculum implementation (Peens, 2018). The readiness of teachers in changing their teaching methods and practices poses a serious threat to curriculum implementation. Maodzwa-Taruvunga and Cross (2012) aver that some teachers are convinced that it was easier to remain with familiar teaching methods instead of focusing on the new policies. Molapo (2016) reveals that CAPS implementation was hindered by insufficient in-service training of Accounting teachers, inadequate interpretation of curriculum modifications, ineffective participation of teachers in the development of the curriculum process, insufficient resources and over-burden with work. The five days workshop strategy for teachers has been regarded as inadequate to the fact that content training is too elementary or deficient for different levels of Accounting teachers (Maodzwa-Taruvunga & Cross, 2012). Msomi, (2014) reveals that teachers were battling to teach new topics like Auditing because they lack content understanding and that there was very little done by the Department of Basic Education to prepare and capacitate teachers regarding the new curriculum. Therefore, this study sought to understand the challenges that Accounting teachers experience when implementing the new curriculum. Maistry (2007) reveals that endless curriculum modifications have jeopardized the quality of teaching and learning in most parts of South Africa township and rural secondary schools.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed at investigating challenges faced by Accounting teachers towards curriculum implementation in the context of curriculum change in South African township secondary schools. The objectives of the study were:

- To identify challenges of implementing Accounting curriculum in a context of curriculum change in selected South African township secondary schools; and
- To investigate teaching strategies used by Accounting teachers in implementing curriculum in line with new teaching methods and approaches.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study found its expression within the following theories: Piaget's theory of cognitive development, Transformative theory of Dirac, and Maslow's motivation theory. Piaget (1977) states that the cognitive development theory is a comprehensive theory about the nature and development of human intelligence. Curriculum reform has brought about so many changes in the strategies and approaches to teaching, learning and assessments. This has been seen to cause instability in teachers' understanding of curriculum and content knowledge, thus challenges in curriculum implementation (Ngwenya, 2014). The belief that teachers' performance has stability and certainty when curriculum and education system is underpinned in Piaget's ideas of assimilation and accommodation. Assimilation occurs when there is modification or change of new information to fit into schemas (what is already known). Stability in the context of this study would be based on the smooth transition where teachers would be retrained and reskilled for them to be able to comprehend the new curriculum. Accommodation refers to change in teaching that would require the school to prepare learners and improve their performance. This would further require the teacher to alter how they enhance their teaching by

using technology, new materials or even bringing expectations into the classroom (Williamson, 2011). Shepard (2019) argues that adapting to alternative teaching methods and approaches can lead to more developed Accounting understandings and competencies.

Transformation theory by Dirac (1927), refers to the changes a quantum state undergoes in the course of time, whereby it moves between positions or orientations in its Hilbert space. The transformational theory is meant to be an inclusive, idealised, and comprehensive model involving the standard structure, features and practices of adult learning. Teachers are expected to implement the new curriculum, in the process they need to adapt to the transformation of such curriculum and be able to work within the new approaches. This may require them to enrol for new pedagogical studies, and attend workshops and seminars in order to upgrade and enhance their skills to be in line with the directives of the new curriculum. Accounting teachers would need to transform themselves by upgrading into studies and programmes that will enhance their content understanding of new accounting topics like auditing, internal controls and also adapt to new approaches of teaching in order to enhance learners creativity, scientific, gathering, scrutinising, communication, organising and interpreting skills (DoE, 2008b).

Another belief is that teachers perform well in curriculum implementation when they are motivated as advocated in Maslow's theory that describes the importance of the hierarchy of needs (Maslow, 1958). Teachers expect their morale and self-esteem to be boosted by recognising them for outstanding performance, being awarded incentives and rewards where befitting. This is a critical matter that may make teachers want to do more than their call of duty and that may strengthen curriculum delivery in the classroom. There is the general notion that the department of education provides very little towards the process of motivating teachers for a successful NCS implementation. Molapo (2016) discloses that the lack of motivation for new curriculum implementation by teachers as well as the poor involvement of teachers in curriculum development process is among the fundamental causes of failure to implement curriculum. Accounting teachings require teaching strategies and methods that promote active student learning and learners that are competitive with other countries in the world (Fortin & Legault, 2010).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research approach and design

In confronting the challenges of implementing Accounting curriculum in a context of change in selected South African township secondary schools, the researchers used a qualitative approach. According to Leedy and Ormrod (2010), qualitative research aims at gaining a deep understanding of specific phenomena. This study also employed a case study design to probe answers to challenges encountered by teachers in the implementation of the new Accounting curriculum. Case studies according to Flyvbjerg (2011), allow researchers to investigate in-depth information about a phenomenon from the participants through social interaction, their thoughts, beliefs and perceptions. This is supported by George and Bennett (2005) who describe a case study as a research design typically used by researchers in social and life situations to probe deeply for understanding of different phenomena in a manner that presents natural settings. The fact that case study constitutes that uniqueness of presenting real-life situations and provides a holistic approach in participants relating to their experiences, made it relevant to dig deep in trying to investigate challenges faced by Accounting teachers in curriculum implementation.

Sampling procedures

Purposive sampling was utilised to choose participants in order to gain insight from the fundamental phenomenon. Creswell (2014) attests that purposive sampling is useful for choosing a certain group with certain distinctive attributes. Accounting teachers with relevant qualifications, teaching Accounting in grades 10-12, formed part of the sample. Seventeen (17) township secondary schools were selected from one South African township, of which four were from Burlington circuit, four from Dukumbane circuit, three from Maphundu circuit, three from Mxenge circuit and three from Isipingo circuit. This constitutes (10 %) of 167 secondary schools offering Accounting as a subject in one selected township. The researchers selected one teacher per school as the likelihood was that a teacher who teaches Accounting might also be teaching EMS in grades 8 or 9. The number of teachers who participated in the study were seventeen (17). Through purposive sampling, one Accounting teacher teaching grades 10-12 was selected from the seventeen (17) schools and was interviewed to respond to the questions relevant to the research study. Further to this, five (5) secondary school principals who were all randomly selected from the sample schools in one selected township were interviewed. They were required to respond as to how they deal with curriculum management regarding the learning and teaching of Accounting in their responsibility as instructional managers and providing instructional leadership. So, if a concrete foundation had been installed for learners in grade 10, the possibility is that they would easily

succeed in grades 11 and 12. The sample was drawn taking into consideration teachers' qualifications and experience in teaching Accounting to be able to draw informed conclusions from answers provided by the participants.

Research instruments

Semi-structured interviews

In this study, semi-structured interviews were used with the researchers acting as facilitators to elicit the participants' insights and views. Semi-structured interviews were acceptable for this study because the participants could give their opinions freely, relate with others and give an understanding of the world around them and express how they defined and gave meaning of the situation in which they found themselves. Interview questions were given to the participants before the interview session so that they would be prepared for their answers. Audio-digital recordings were used to conduct semi-structured interviews to generate data in order to probe teachers' challenges of implementing Accounting curriculum in a context of change. Neuman (2014, p. 57) "advocates that an interview is an interaction between two individuals where one person wants to obtain specific information from the other". A set of open-ended questions were prepared and posed to teachers for them to provide answers on what they view as challenges when they implement curriculum as well as the teaching methods and strategies they use during teaching and learning.

Document analysis

Document analysis was employed to gather evidence on how teachers implement curriculum in grade 10 where fundamental basic principles of Accounting are introduced as FET phase begins. According to Bowen (2009, p. 77), "document analysis is a form of qualitative research in which documents are interpreted by the researchers to give voice and meaning around an assessment topic". The relevant documents that were viewed in this study included policy documents such as National Curriculum Statements, Subject Assessment Guidelines, National Protocol for Assessments, annual teaching plans, work schedules, lesson plans, learners' workbooks and other documents relating to teaching and learning and assessment.

Data analysis

According to Sarantakos (2007, p. 24), data analysis "is a process of processing data and converting it into meaningful statements". The interviews were transcribed *verbatim* from audio records to text to present and analyse them according to the research objectives. Analysed documents were incorporated into themes similar to how interview transcripts were analysed. The responses from the interviews were analysed using content analysis that was done with the use of thematic, common and recurring words. Open coding was used, and groupings were formed, evaluated and gathered into special themes. In the process, data was scrutinised, polished, converted and shaped for the purpose of finding valuable information, indicating decisions and supporting conclusions. However, for the purpose of presenting results, the following pseudo names were used to keep participants anonymous: Peter; Sanele; Nosipho; Tom; Nobuhle; Vee; Mpilo; Thoko; Tshepo; Fikile; Young; Aubrey; Andiswa; Terence; Patson; Vukile; and Dee. Consequently, the following themes were identified from the in-depth interviews and document analysis:

Themes and subthemes from interviews:

- Adaptation to curriculum change and content understanding and coverage
- Shortages of teaching and learning resources
- Challenges faced by Accounting teachers in curriculum implementation in South African township secondary schools.

Themes from document analysis:

- Content coverage
- Assessment controls
- Planning controls

Trustworthiness of the study

The researchers were passionate about ensuring that the data generated did not deviate from the research objectives and in the process ensured trustworthiness that was not compromised and was composed of baseline features such as credibility, dependability, transferability and confirmability. For this assurance, the researchers took the transcriptions of data that was generated from the interviews back to the participants to ascertain and verify whether indeed the transcribed and interpreted data represented the true answers from the participants' experiences in of curriculum implementation process. Creswell (2014) and Patton (2002) aver that qualitative

researchers should consider doing member checking, detailed data transcription and triangulation to ensure that rigour and trustworthiness of the study are maintained.

Ethical considerations

According to Kelly (2009), the researchers use different techniques to generate data that are set depending on the type of research problem that is being investigated. These instruments could include, among others, interviews and document analyses. Permission was received from the circuit manager and the district director as well as the provincial Head of Department to generate data with Accounting teachers. Therefore, the researchers organised to meet with these participants in order to agree on appointment dates for interviews and to clearly explain how the research project was going to unfold as well as the issues of safety and confidentiality.

Therefore, it was imperative that participants were made aware of the research process, explaining and disclosing the purpose, time duration and transparency of the research proceedings.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings from interviews

Adaptation to curriculum, content understanding and coverage

It is evident from participants that there are so many challenges that are confronting Accounting teachers regarding the level of pedagogical content knowledge. Almost all participants cited that they were struggling with most of the topics as well as the approach to be followed when teaching Accounting in the classroom. The transition in terms of reskilling and training when the new curriculum was introduced was not adequately done as only workshops that did not really tap into the new curriculum content were organised by the Department of Education. Manyage, Sithubi, Mudau and Ravhuhali (2022) attest that the space and content of in-service training (INSET) assume a one-size-fits-all approach, which sometimes creates more problems as content knowledge and pedagogical content differ in context and depth. Some of the participants stated as follows:

“My learners have not adapted to the new Accounting curriculum...the introduction of new topics like internal controls, auditing, analysis and interpretation has made Accounting to be very hard to understand. This interpretation needs learners to think deeply and have diverse thinking of businesses, I find the new curriculum really complicated for me to teach and for learners to learn”, said Nobuhle.

“Teaching Accounting is not easy to grade 10 learners.....they show lack of foundation knowledge and basic understanding of Accounting concepts. It means in grades 8 and 9, they were not taught the basics of Accounting perfectly. Learners in grades 8 and 9 are taught EMS by non-accounting specialists, how can they teach Accounting section? They could only teach Business Studies and leave Accounting”, stated Tom.

Shortage of learning and teaching resources

Quintile's ranking indicates the provision of wealth and resources of each school. Most township secondary schools are ranked between quintiles one and three, with a clear indication that the level of poverty is very high. Although these schools receive more allocation in terms of norms and standards compared to schools in quintiles four and five, funding of teaching and learning resources is never enough because these schools only rely on the government's funding as they are not allowed to charge school fees. Hoadley and Jansen (2002) aver that quintile 1-3 schools always experience a financial burden to top up their operational resources for teaching and learning. Mabusela, Ngidi and Imenda (2016) argue that curriculum implementation entails resource materials (learners' books, learning aids and workbooks) for teachers and learners to fulfil their role acceptably in the curriculum execution practice. Ntshangase (2017) agrees that some schools are even battling with basic resources like floor space, desks and textbooks, as well as human resources which contribute to the overcrowding of learners in the classroom and the need to share textbooks. The participants attest as follows:

“We are quintile 3 and a no-fee school, we mainly depend on the Department for resources, we are so under-resourced such that there is no other thing that we understand except being under-resourced”, said Siphosho who is the principal of a school.

Shanda: “We are quintile four (fee-paying school), meaning we are purported to be a rich school, whereas the reality is that we are very poor as many of our learners come from disadvantaged communities, their parents are not working and some learners come from the child-headed families where there is no parental love, support and guidance. All this impacts negatively on teaching and learning and successful curriculum implementation”.

Challenges faced by Accounting teachers in curriculum implementation

Curriculum changes that have been implemented over the years have affected teachers in different ways. Whilst the curriculum was set to redress the inequalities of the past and bring about quality public education to the people of South Africa, it brought a hard toll for teachers. This was evident when the Department of Education

kept on reviewing curricula in the plight of improving challenges faced. Guthrie (2012) argues that the Department of Education tried to 'fix' the curriculum by repeatedly revising it with the hope that it would improve implementation, whereas teachers became tired of such a change, and more challenges piled up.

Subsequently, there is a belief that Accounting textbooks used in the South African schooling system are written in a language that is far beyond the cognitive levels of Accounting learners. All participants stated that the usage of English as the instructional language creates another critical challenge in curriculum implementation. Modise and Segalo (2020) posit that (80%) of the learners in the Accounting classroom struggle with reading, writing and speaking skills which also affect their academic performances. Matthew (2014) concurs that Accounting textbooks are not written with the Accounting learners in mind. As a result, textbooks lack simplified and clarifying examples and explanations that could assist Accounting learners to comprehend and understand better what is expected of them in the subject. Learners are unable to understand instructions and grasp some basic Accounting concepts because Accounting is not taught in their mother tongue but in English which is their second language. To support the above narrative participants revealed the following:

Dee said, "Language barrier is not only a challenge for learners, but most Accounting teachers in township secondary schools teach Accounting in IsiZulu because they feel learners do battle in understanding English. This poses a great challenge because Accounting terminology cannot be translated verbatim into IsiZulu and the subject is purely examined in English".

"The language that is used in Accounting textbooks is very difficult for learners to understand, they fail to comprehend and analyse transactions and end up perceiving Accounting to be difficult. This negative attitude has impacted badly on the overall subject.....The failure rate has gone high, last year Accounting results dropped from (53%) to (32%)..... it's really bad and this has resulted in quite a number of learners running away from Accounting and opting for other subjects", said Vukile.

Besides, the pedagogical content for each subject needs to align learners' needs with the subject, taking into consideration that curriculum is streamlined time and again to respond to the demands of a country in meeting its obligation. Teaching strategies also need to evolve with time. Some teachers are challenged in using a variety of teaching methods in teaching and supporting their learners. Crispel and Kasperski (2021, p. 1086) promulgate that "experienced teachers tend not to change their current practices easily because these are rooted in their beliefs and in the practical knowledge that they have accumulated during their years of teaching". So, while changes in curriculum "theoretically require teachers to make significant shifts with respect to its content and their instructional methods alike, in practice many teachers either resist implementing curriculum change or adapt the curriculum to suit their own practices"(Thumvichit, 2021, p. 22). This means teachers just incorporate teaching strategies into their current practices with little or no substantive change. It is understood that a teaching strategy is influenced by a variety of factors including the age of the learner and the content. Phakathi (2019) asserts that a variety of teaching strategies and methods must be used by a teacher as effective learning is measured through meaningful learning. Furthermore, Gouws (2008) avers that reconceptualization which was created by curriculum changes in Accounting or any other subject has a direct bearing on teaching, learning and assessment methods and strategies, for it implied a need to transform teaching and assessment practice: teachers now had to follow new approaches to lesson planning, actual teaching and methods of assessment.

Therefore, participants were of the same view that normally when they introduce a new topic, they first explain the objectives, basic concepts, give practical examples in the process and try to adopt other relevant approaches that will make the topic understood better by the learners. Killen (2016) posits that direct instruction as a teacher-centred teaching method is one of the most effective ways of promoting learners' learning as it has a history of strong research support, but the success of direct instruction depends primarily on the teacher's enthusiasm and efforts. As a teacher-dominant strategy, the emphasis is teaching in small steps by providing learners practice after each step, guiding learners during the initial practice and providing all learners with a high level of successful practice. Participants shared the same view as follows:

Andiswa: "No matter how curriculum, teaching and assessments strategies and approaches could change, teacher centred method remains the core towards successful curriculum delivery in class....There is no method that may be operational without a teacher being at the centre of teaching and learning. Teaching is basically about teachers, they teach and learners learn".

"Most of my teaching is based on me as a teacher leading the way in the presentation of lessons and then advance into other methods such learners finding themselves into understanding what they have learned and translate it into problem-solving, research, presentations and interpretation....all this happens after the teacher has laid a foundation", said Young.

Nevertheless, the learner-centred approach encourages learners to come out of their shells and become active participants during the learning process. According to Maphalala (2016), the learner-centred technique promotes learners to fully participate in the learning process by mastering transferable skills such as research skills, investigation skills, report writing and interpersonal skills, analytical and problem-solving skills, good listening

and communication skills. This is confirmed by Sikhombo (2018) who believes that cooperative learning promotes and improves communication skills and self-confidence in learners. Jacobs, Vilakasi and Gawe (2016) argue that once teacher has set clear objectives for their class, they need to create a learning-friendly classroom environment. This is congruent with Piaget's theory of cognitive development stating that teaching and learning are modified and transformed based on the educator's cognitive structures, social interaction, previous learning and environment (Kutz, 1991). Furthermore, Accounting teachers will have to learn and have an understanding of new topics in the new curriculum and also change their teaching strategies and methods to be in line with new approaches to teaching and assessment as directed by the new curriculum or aligned with the demands of the 4th industrial revolution. This is what the participants had to say:

"I use more of learner centred approach in order to allow all learners to participate...I want them to be involved by sharing ideas as learners understand better when taught by their peers moreover, the new curriculum dictates that learners must develop a sense of independence and be able to draw informed decisions that are competitive to the business world", emphasized Tom.

"I normally group and segregate my learners into three groups according to their capabilities, high flyers, average and struggling learners....This motivates and enhances their interest in the subject as they work freely with other peers. It also allows me to plan in the manner that allows learners to unleash their capabilities without putting pressure that may create a negative attitude toward Accounting", confirmed Peter.

"Learner-based approach is the order of the day in my class....instead of using more of textbook and narrative methods, I group my learners and allow them to do more presentations based on practical scenarios. This motivates them and makes them interested in Accounting as they deal with practical issues that they see happening in real-life situations", stated Mpilo.

Findings from document analysis

Content coverage

This was done to understand whether the curriculum has been covered as per the outline of topics to be covered in grade 10 in terms of content. Subject policies, SAG, work schedules, ATPs, lesson plans, programme of assessments, and learners' workbooks had to be inspected to gather relevant information on how schools are managing content coverage.

Accordingly, salaries and wages, reporting, managerial Accounting, and VAT are the main topics that were expected to be covered in grade 10 during the inspection. The results from the inspection of the relevant documents, namely, work schedules, annual teaching plans (ATPs), lesson plans, and learners' workbooks are evident that township secondary schools are struggling to complete the prescribed content in grade 10. In the mid-October, (23%) of schools had not covered salaries and wages journals, whilst (41%) seems they struggled to cover the reporting section, (47%) were not close to completing managerial Accounting and 41% were not even sure whether they would be able to finish VAT before the end of the year. It is worth noting that all schools had managed to cover the basic recordings which, should be the extension of grades 7, 8 and 9 work. Participants have based their struggles on mainly the challenges in EMS in GET phase, where they argue that justice is not done with the coverage of the Accounting section and thus compromise the basics. They said, most teachers teaching EMS are not Accounting specialists, hence, when learners reach grade 10, teachers must first teach the basics that should have been covered in grades 7, 8 and 9, which makes it difficult for them to cover the grade 10 work.

Consequently, Ezeagba (2014) confirms that Accounting township secondary schools are faced with two main challenges: the teaching which is not adequate and the learning which is faced by demotivated learners on the other hand. The above results are an indication that Accounting teachers do battle with the teachings of Accounting in grade 10 which serves as the cornerstone for the basic principles at the FET level. Ngwenya (2014) concludes that teachers do not teach grade 10 Accounting content effectively with the view that other parts of the content will be taught at a later stage in grades 11 and 12 and teachers only focused on scanning the curriculum and only teach learners lower-order questions. This means teachers in grade 10 see it as not important to comply with the directives of the curriculum and they end up not finishing the syllabus. Curriculum changes from C2005 to RNCS, NCS and eventually CAPS have been increased and improved to levels of specifications and that has led to greater prescriptiveness (DoE, 2011). However, teachers seem to battle to adapt to such specifications due to either resistance or incompetence (Samuel, 2008). Another belief that teachers perform well in curriculum implementation when they are motivated as advocated by Maslow's theory of morale and self-esteem, seems to be evident from the findings as there is little effort for teachers to adapt to curriculum changes.

Assessment controls

Subject Assessment Guideline (SAG) together with assessment evidence from assessment grids, programme of assessments, mark schedules, workbooks and exercise books were inspected to understand whether schools do adhere to the directives of assessments to be completed in grade 10 as prescribed in the subject assessment guideline.

Thus, assignments, controlled tests, class tests, mid-year examinations, projects, trialexaminations, and year-end examinations are the formal assessment tasks that are prescribed by the Department of Basic Education for Accounting grade 10 learners across the academic year. Positively, the inspection of SAG, National Protocol on Assessment, learners' workbooks and exercise books, learners' mark schedules and assessment grid revealed that all schools had complied with the prescripts of the Accounting Subject Assessment Guidelines (SAG) (2008a) in terms of the form and number of assessments pieces/activities needed to be completed. It must, however, be noted that the research unveiled a challenge in the correlation between content coverage and the assessment. How is it possible to have mastered the assessment protocols having not covered the content to have been taught? Was this assessment authentic? Killen (2016) emphasises that assessment should be authentic, developmental and integrated into teaching instead of being a standalone or added at the end of the activity. Furthermore, Killen (2016) maintains that there should be a correlation between teaching and assessing and assessment is supposed to provide the teacher with information about progress in learning and teaching.

It was evident from the above discussion that, although teachers are familiar with changes and expectations of the curriculum policy prospects, they are failing to adapt to the actual expected levels of teaching and assessment. There is no rationale in not completing what should have been taught, however, be in line with the directives of assessment. This means that teachers mainly focus on what they will account for, like the moderation of formal assessments which the DBE focuses on and seem not to do justice to curriculum implementation holistically. "This could be because there have been too many changes in the curriculum, and teachers have become too policy resistant or too policy compliant" (Ngwenya, 2014, p. 178). Teachers are proving not to be true agents in shaping policy for curriculum delivery in the classroom. Spillane, Reiser and Gomez (2006) aver that when teachers are confronted with change, they become uncertain about what changes are required of them, and eventually have doubts about their ability to succeed in the implementation of the new curriculum. The identified gap in this document analysis may be one of the factors that contribute to a high failure rate in Accounting during the final examination at grade 12.

Planning and Control

Evidence gathered from teachers indicates that there is little compliance when it comes to planning and control systems for Accounting curriculum implementation from the seventeen township secondary schools presented as the sample for the study. Although (100%) of schools appeared to have Accounting workbooks, the research revealed that only (30%) of schools were compliant in terms of processing, marking and correcting learners' work. Work appeared to be done haphazardly in (70%) of schools, not marked, with no traces of signatures from subject teachers, and no evidence of engagements and corrections made. This compromises curriculum implementation as workbooks form an integral part of content coverage. The trend continues to suggest that township secondary schools are not on par with proper curriculum implementation planning as only (59%) of participants were in possession of the annual teaching plans (ATPs) and (53%) were able to show their programme of assessments. Of the seventeen schools, only ten had evidence of lesson plans in their files, which is only (59%), meaning (41%) was not preparing for curriculum delivery in the classroom. Further to this, the research also revealed that analysis of results is not done by most schools, evidently showing that only (41%) of participants presented item analyses and (47%) had proof of diagnostic analyses. Out of the (59%) and (53%) of participants who did not have item analyses and diagnostic analyses respectively, more than (70%) of them did not even know what the documents are and what do they seek to achieve. Another critical aspect in planning and curriculum implementation is the moderation and control of work by instructional managers in order to register whether the work done towards curriculum delivery and implementation is in line with the policy prescripts for a subject. When inspecting the moderation reports for the participants, only nine out of seventeen schools (53%) were able to present such reports, with others claiming that moderation does take place, however, they could not find their reports. That was an indication that planning was really a challenge at those schools.

The findings from the above analysis show that most teachers in township secondary schools have not adapted to the directives and expectations of new curriculum. The belief is that teachers are the drivers of success in implementing new curriculum. Teachers are also perceived as agents in shaping the understanding of curriculum policies and implementation that translate into classroom practices (Wright, Crooks, Hunter, Krumm & Balgopal, 2021). With many teachers viewing themselves as 'administrators' because of intense paperwork under the dispensation of the new curriculum, they have opted not to follow the pedagogic values and practices of the new curriculum regarding the shifts in teaching and assessment. In fact, teachers are so demotivated to pursue the expectations of the new curriculum because of a number of reasons. Amongst the findings by Molapo (2016); Msomi, (2014) and Offorma (2013), is the lack of motivation for teachers to implement the new

curriculum. One of the fundamental reasons for the failure of teachers to adapt to the new curriculum is the lack of support from the relevant authorities during the transformation process of the curriculum as advocated by Madondo (2021) from the transformation theory. Another common factor is the assumption that old teachers tend to be very sceptical about changing their old ways of teaching based on the way they were trained (Samuel, 2008: 5), hence they tend to continue with their old pedagogic practices and values in implementing the new curriculum.

CONCLUSION

This article concludes that many Accounting teachers have not adapted to the pedagogical content of the new curriculum and teachers are faced with a number of challenges during curriculum implementation. It was also found that supervision of learning and teaching is compromised because most of the departmental heads who are deemed to be custodians of learning and teaching are not qualified in Accounting; as a result, they are not able to monitor and moderate the pedagogical part of Accounting, but rather focus on subjects like Economics and Business Economics. The study further concludes that subject advisors are not always available to render support and guidance on content understanding to teachers and offer capacity building where areas of improvement have been identified. Moreover, the language barrier is one of the fundamental challenges that have a negative impact on the Accounting curriculum implementation. English as the language of learning and teaching contributes to challenges that negatively affect curriculum implementation in Accounting. Accounting textbooks used in the South African schooling system are written in a language that is far beyond the cognitive levels of learners.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study intended to investigate the challenges encountered by Accounting teachers towards curriculum implementation in the context of curriculum change in South African township secondary schools. The recommendations are proposed as follows:

- A clear policy on how to retrain and reskill Accounting teachers on the new curriculum topics and teaching methods and approaches that teachers have to adopt during learning, teaching and assessment must be developed by the DBE.
- The DBE should consider reviewing CAPS with regard to EMS in the GET phase and make Accounting a stand-alone subject in grades 8 and 9. This will allow schools to employ teachers who are qualified in teaching Accounting and have pedagogical content knowledge in the subject so as to provide strong Accounting basics from as early as the GET phase.
- The implementation of performance measures such as IQMS, QMS, CPTD and EPMD should be improved by the Department of Education and be geared towards the development of pedagogical content knowledge and curriculum implementation rather than just incentives as perceived by teachers.
- The DBE must work in collaboration with Accounting textbook authors and consider reviewing the contents to be in line with the present Accounting curriculum and what is being practised in the real world. These textbooks should also respond to the technological developments necessitated by the 4IR.
- The Department of Basic Education must enhance Performance Measures (PPMs) such as PPM 104 and PPM 209. These performance measures are indicators that determine whether indeed curriculum implementation does take place as it should through tracing academic performance, teacher attendance, learner attendance, and challenges faced by both teachers and learners during learning and teaching.

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